

The Translation of the Indonesian Noun Phrases into English

Ni Luh Ketut Mas Indrawati¹, Ida Ayu Made Puspani²

^{1,2}Faculty of Humanities Udayana University

ABSTRACT: The title of this research is the translation of the Indonesian noun phrases (NPs) into English. NPs are groups of words of which heads are nouns. Head nouns can be expanded to the right or to the left in a phrase. The discussion in this research was limited to the NPs with expansion to the right. Extending a head noun to the right in Indonesian can be done by adding modifiers with or without a determiner. The purpose of this study is to describe the types of modifiers of the Indonesian NPs with expansion to the right and their translation into English. This research is categorized as a descriptive qualitative study, the data were taken from the translations of the folk tales by the fourth-semester students of The English Department Faculty of Humanities, Udayana University, with the application of observation methods and documentation techniques. The data were then analyzed by applying the theory of translation proposed by Vinay and Darbelnet. The results showed that the types of Indonesian NPs have modifier elements in the form of nouns or noun phrases, adjectives or adjective phrases, verbs or verb phrases, prepositional phrases, clauses, and appositives. The Indonesian NPs with right expansion were translated into the English NPs with the right and left expansions.

KEYWORDS: Equivalent, Noun phrases, Translation.

INTRODUCTION

Translation is an effort to replace the meaning of the source language (SL) text with the equivalent text meaning in the target language (TL). Larson (1984: 3) describes translation as the transfer of meaning from the SL to the TL. Meanwhile, Vinay and Darbelnet (2000; 84-91) view that the transfer of the equivalence of the SL text to the TL text is the most crucial thing in translation, considering that each language has its own system and culture.

A noun phrase (NP) is defined as a phrase or group of words whose head is a noun. The noun as the head of the NP can be expanded to the left and/or to the right, Moeliono, et al. (2017). For example, from the Indonesian noun, *baju* 'clothes', a NP can be formed by adding the word *tiga* 'three', *buah* 'numeral specifier', *baru* 'new', and *itu* 'that' so that it becomes *tiga buah baju baru itu* 'the three new clothes. The word *tiga* 'three' and *buah* 'is usually referred to as a numeral specifier' which extends the head noun, *baju* 'clothes' to the left, while *baru* 'new' serves as a modifier that provides more information about the head noun, *baju* 'clothes' and *itu* 'that' in the phrase has a determining function that limits or determines the word *baju* 'clothes', as the noun head. Both *itu* 'that' and *baru* 'new' extend the head noun *baju* 'clothes' to the right.

Meanwhile Kroeger (2005: 87) views NPs as phrasal constituents that have nouns as heads. NPs in English can function as subjects, primary or secondary objects, and objects of the preposition. The various types of non-head constituents that may appear in phrases in a large number of languages are divided into three classes namely: determiner, complement, and adjunct. Kroeger (2005: 90) states that the basic order of constituents in the English NPs (except determiner and complement) can be patterned as follows: Determinants-Adjectives-Noun- Prepositional Phrase. It can be seen in the following example:

- a. that little dog under the table. (Determiner -Adjective -Noun-Prepositional Phrase)
- b. a secret admirer in the Ministry of Education. (Determiner -Adjective -Noun-Prepositional Phrase).

Viewed from the structure of the Indonesian and English NPs, the two languages have different ways of packaging the meaning. This intrigued researchers to investigate the translation of the Indonesian NPs into English by students of The English Department, Faculty of Science Culture, Udayana University. The problems raised were: (1) what types of modifiers of the Indonesian NPs with expansion to the right were found in the Indonesian folktales translated; (2) how were the Indonesian NPs with expansion to the right as the source language (SL) was translated into English

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This research was descriptive qualitative, and the data source was the results of the translation of ten Indonesian folklores as the source language (SL) into English as the target language (TL) by the four-semester students of The English Department faculty of Humanities, Udayana University.

All the Indonesian NPs with expansion to the right and their English translations were the primary data in this study. The secondary data used to clarify the concept and analysis were taken from the results of the previous research. The data were descriptive-qualitatively analyzed and presented informally based on the types of the modifiers of the Indonesian NPs with expansion to the right and their translation into English

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This section discusses the Indonesian NPs with expansion to the right focusing on the types of non-head elements of the Indonesian NPs found in the folktales translated, and analysing the English translations

Indonesian Noun Phrases with expansion to the right and their translation into English

Noun expansion to the right in Indonesian can be done by adding a modifier with or without a determiner. The determiner whose position is to the right of the noun can be in the form of demonstrative pronouns, honorific pronouns, possessive pronouns as in the example: *buku baru di atas meja* ‘the new book on the table’, the head noun of the NP is in the form of noun, *buku* ‘book’, *baru* ‘new’, adjective, and *di atas meja* ‘on the table’, prepositional phrase as a modifier. The types of modifiers or non-head elements of the Indonesian NPs found in the data are described as follows:

Indonesian Noun phrases with Adjectives as Modifiers and Their Translations in English

No.	SL	TL
1	pondok baru	new hut
2	gadis cantik	the beautiful girl
3	telaga biru	blue lake
4	sikap buruk	bad attitude
5	bau harum	nice smell

Data (1) - (5) in the SL column show that the nouns, the words in bold: *pondok* ‘hut’, *gadis* ‘girl’, *telaga* ‘lake’, *sikap* ‘attitude’, and *bau* ‘smell’ as the head nouns of the phrases are expanded to the right by adding adjectives; *baru* ‘new’, *cantik* ‘beautiful’, *biru* ‘blue’, *buruk* ‘bad’, *harum* ‘fragrant’. This FN is translated into Target Language (TL) with a noun expansion structure to the left in SL. Head nouns: hut, girl, lake, attitude, and smell are expanded to the left with adjective modifiers: new, beautiful, blue, bad, and nice.

Indonesian Noun phrases with Nouns as modifiers and Their Translations in English

Nouns can be modifiers of the head nouns of the Indonesian NPs with right expansion. This can be seen in the following data:

No.	SL	TL
6	kekuasaan kerajaan	the kingdom’s power .
7	...hasil pembekuan lahar di dekat sebuah pohon beringin	...the rocks from the freezing lava near a banyan tree
8	...selalu memberinya hadiah perhiasan	always give her a gift of jewelry
9	...ia memasukkan tangannya ke dalam mulut kijang tersebut dengan hati-hati	...he put his hand into the mouth of the deer carefully
10	penguasa danau	the ruler of the lake

In data (6) - (10), it can be seen that the head nouns: *kekuasaan* ‘power’, *pohon* ‘tree’, *hadiah* ‘gift’, *mulut* ‘mouth’, and *penguasa* ‘ruler’ are expanded to the right with modifiers: kingdom, banyan, jewelry, deer, and lake which are also categorized as nouns. In data (6) the NP *kekuasaan kerajaan* is translated into the kingdom's power, **power** as the head noun is expanded to the left with the noun possessor, kingdom's as a modifier. While in data (7) the NP, *pohon beringin* is translated as the banyan **tree**, the tree is the head noun while banyan is a modifying noun so that the head noun in the SL gets an expansion to the left in the TL. Data (8)-(10) shows the same thing, that is the NP with the head noun is expanded to the right; *hadiah perhiasan* is translated into **gift** of jewellery, and the head noun, **gift** is expanded to the right with the Prepositional Phrase (PP) as a modifier. Similar to data (9), *mulut kijang* is translated into the **mouth** of the deer, and (10) *penguasa danau* into the **ruler** of the lake.

Indonesian Noun phrases with verbs as modifiers and Their Translations in English

Head nouns in the Indonesian NPs as SL can be expanded to the right with verbs as modifiers, as shown in the following data:

No.	SL	TL
11	<i>perjalanan menyusuri pantai selatan</i>	the journey along the south coast
12	<i>batu menangis</i>	the crying stone
13	<i>telaga berair jernih agak kebiruan.</i>	lake with clear slightly bluish water
14	<i>senyum menyebalkan</i>	<i>cynical</i> smile
15	<i>karung berisi kacang koro yang berat</i>	<i>the heavy beans</i> sacks

Data (11) and (13) show that the NPs with the head noun expanded to the right with verbs as modifiers in SL, are translated into the NPs with the head nouns expanded to the right with the PP modifiers. In data (11), *perjalanan menyusuri pantai selatan* is translated into the **journey** along the south coast; on data (13) *telaga berair jernih agak kebiruan* is translated into lake with clear slightly bluish water.

Data (12) shows that the SL NP with the head noun expanded to the right with verb modifier, *batu menangis* in the SL, is translated into NP with the head noun expanded to the left with the determiner, 'the', and the present participle 'crying' as the modifier. While in data (14) the NP in the SL with a head noun, *senyum* is expanded to the right with the verb *menyebalkan* as modifier is translated into the English (TL) NP with a head noun, **smile** which is expanded to the left with an adjective, 'cynical' as the modifier. In data (15) the SL NP with the head noun, *karung* expanded to the right with a verb phrase modifier, '*berisi kacang koro yang berat*', is translated into TL NP with the head noun, **sacks** expanded to the left with the NP, the heavy beans

Indonesian Noun Phrases with Prepositional Phrases as Modifiers and Their Translations in English

No.	SL	TL
16	<i>kampung di pinggir danau minanjau</i>	a village on the outskirts of lake Minanjau
17	<i>pekerjaannya di sawah</i>	his work in the rice fields
18	<i>ikan mas di dalam hutan</i>	goldfish in the forest
19	<i>pasar di kota</i>	the market in the city
20	<i>sebuah pondok di tepi hutan</i>	a cottage on the edge of the forest

Data (16)-(20) show that the SL NP's head nouns; *kampung, pekerjaannya, ikan mas, pasar, and pondok* are expanded to the right with PP; *di pinggir danau minanjau, di sawah, di dalam hutan, di kota and di tepi hutan* are translated into the TL NPs with the head noun expanded to the right with the PP modifiers as well; **a village on the outskirts of lake Minanjau, his work in the rice fields, goldfish in the forest, the market in the city, and a cottage on the edge of the forest.**

Indonesian Noun Phrases with Possessive Pronoun as Modifier and Their Translations in English

No.	SL	TL
21	<i>daerah mereka tiba-tiba ditemukan air</i>	their area suddenly found water
22	<i>anjing pemburunya Tumang</i>	his hunting dog Tumang
23	<i>Pada suatu hari Si Kabayan disuruh mertuanya...</i>	One day, Kabayan was told by his father-in-law ...
24	<i>bagaimana nanti jika doaku tidak tertuju kepada Abah</i>	what if my prayers are not directed to him
25	<i>Suami perempuan ini telah lama meninggal.</i>	This woman's husband died a long time ago.

Data (21)-(25) show that the head nouns; *daerah, anjing pemburu, mertua, doa, and suami* are expanded to the right with possessive pronouns as modifiers: *mereka*, data (21), *-nya* data (22) and (23); *-ku*, data (24); *perempuan*, data (25). The NPs in the SL are translated into NPs with expansions to the left in the TL, as shown in the TL data column (21) - (25), their **area**, his **hunting dog**, his **father-in-law**, my **prayers**, and the woman's **husband**.

Indonesian Noun Phrases with Noun Compounds and Their Translations in English

Moeliono et al. (2017:325) state that a noun or NP can be expanded with another noun or NP as the head by adding the conjunction *dan* in Indonesian. The NP with compound nouns as modifiers can be found in the data sources as follows:

No.	SL	TL
26	<i>makanan dan minuman yang enak-enak</i>	exquisite food and drinks
27	<i>bulan dan tahun berlalu.</i>	months and years passed.
28	<i>lapar dan dahaganya</i>	her hunger and thirst
29	<i>bau harum dan bau busuk tersebut telah saling menetralsir</i>	the fragrance and stench have neutralized <i>each other</i> .
30	<i>seorang dewa dan seorang dewi yang karena kesalahan yang dibuatnya di kayangan</i>	a god and goddess who made a mistake in the heaven

Data (26) – (30) show that NPs in the SL are formed with head nouns that are extended to the right by the conjunction and: *makanan dan minuman, bulan dan tahun, lapar dan dahaganya, bau harum dan bau busuk tersebut, and dewa dan seorang dewi*. The NPs are translated into the NPs with expansion to the right with a compound noun as modifiers; **food** and **drinks, months** and **years, hunger** and **thirst, fragrance** and **stench, and a god** and **goddess**.

Indonesian Noun Phrases with Appositives as Modifiers and Their Translations in English

Nouns can be expanded with both restrictive and non-restrictive appositives to form NPs in Indonesian. The following data show the NPs whose head nouns can be expanded to the right with non-restrictive appositive; both head and appositive elements can replace the head nouns.

No.	SL	TL
31	<i>Tumang, sang anjing jelmaan dewa</i>	Tumang , the god incarnate as a dog
32	<i>Raden Jaka Bandem, salah seorang dari putera Prabu Brawijaya terakhir,</i>	Raden Jaka Bandem , one of the last sons of King Brawijaya,

Data (31) and (32) in the SL column show that the head nouns in the Indonesian NPs are expanded to the right with appositive so that both the head noun, *Tumang* data (31), and the appositive of the *sang anjing jelmaan dewa* can replace the head noun, as well as data (32) *Raden Jaka Bandem* as the head noun and *salah seorang dari putera Prabu Brawijaya terakhir*, as an appositive. The two NPs are translated into the TL with NPs whose head nouns are extended to the right which has appositives as modifiers as shown in the TL column, **Tumang, the god incarnate as a dog** and for data (32) **Raden Jaka Bandem one of the last sons of King Brawijaya**.

Indonesian Noun Phrases with Relative Clauses as Modifiers and Their Translations in English

Expansion of nouns to the right can also be done by adding a clause as a modifier and the modifying clause is called a relative clause. Relative clauses in Indonesian are always preceded by the word *yang*. NP with relative clause modifier can be seen in the following data

No.	SL	TL
33	<i>Jenazah-jenazah yang dimakamkan dengan cara ini</i>	The bodies that are buried in this way
34	<i>air yang keluar dari bebatuan</i>	water coming out of the rocks
35	<i>daerah yang tergolong sulit air</i>	an area that is classified as difficult water
36	<i>ibu yang tetap mencintai anaknya</i>	a mother who still loves her child
37	<i>kawan yang tak terpisahkan</i>	inseparable friends

The head nouns in the SL data (33)- (37) are expanded to the right by adding relative clauses with the word *yang*. The NPs are translated into TL with nouns expanded to the right as in data (33)-(36) which are preceded by a relative pronoun, **that** in data (33) and (35), and in (34) with the present participle through the omission of the pronoun. Meanwhile, data (37) the NP with extension to the right with the relative clause as a modifier is translated into TL with the NP with nouns extended to the left using an adjective modifier, **inseparable`**.

CONCLUSION

Based on the discussion above, it can be concluded that the translations of the Indonesian noun phrases into English can be described as Noun phrases with head nouns extended to the right in Indonesian as the source language (SL) are performed with modifiers in the forms of adjectives, nouns, verbs, prepositional phrases, pronouns, possessive nouns, compound nouns, appositives, and relative clauses. All these types of modifiers were found in the ten folk tales translated by students. Noun phrases with head nouns extended to the right were translated into English as the TL, with noun phrases extended to the right and also with noun phrases expanded to the left.

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